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Examine teacher perceptions regarding capacity building from the prospective of core development aspect in pre Education of children

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Abstract

The study show result whose teacher of ecce gain refresher courses, performed better development in children. This finding provides evidence that the training courses help to build the capability of teacher and positive impact on learning and teaching. Descriptive studies include Quantative analysis. A questionnaire tool use for collect data for sample and cluster sampling technique use for this studies. Population of this study school teacher make and female whose teaching in ecce. SPSS 27 use for data analysis. In descriptive statistics use mean and standard deviation, infertial statistics use compare to means group by independent t test. Findings of this research according to three core aspects have significant difference but some aspect have no significant affects in both gender and geographic location. Conclusion from this study refresher courses are essential factor for improving capacity building of teacher for betterment of ecce. In future different aspect of development in child capacity build perception need to be search that make learning more effective for society. In some questions surprisingly no significant difference show in gender group and location wise. Some aspect of variable showing significant difference in gender wise and geographic location. The result show that the

focus on teacher refresher course for capacity building paly initial role for improvement core development aspect. The study limited to a district Bahawalnagar and respective tehsil. Which generalized ability of result. In future this studies help to explore more aspect of development that helps to maintain the effectiveness learning for children.

Keywords: *Teacher Perceptions, Capacity Building, Core Development, Early Childhood Education, Professional Development*

1. Introduction

Early child education consider essential for modern society. Nowadays in international scenario educationalist consider it mile stone for progressive society. In Pakistan early childhood care education initiative in 2017. Different organization helps to develop and enhance this initiative in positive way to progress. Different trainings conducted by the government to enhance the teaching skills. In education system of Pakistan much gaps found but in day to day progress government minimize the resistance. In these days government promote the early child care education. Early childhood education contain one year of education before the regular education. Ecce trained teacher in well prepared ecce room trained the children. Teacher use different techniques to gives concept of different things.(Ali et al., 2025) Teacher use different hand material which helps to understand the concept. Government provides ecce kits to teacher with fully equipped skills. (SED, 2020)

In this research we basically evaluate the effectiveness of ecce classroom in context of societal adjustment. Ecce learning promotes skills of individual. Different trainings and refresh courses are offered to ecce teacher for the effectiveness of this program by the help of PACTA. If ecce rooms properly use by the teacher it helps better understanding of child and learning experiences. Different trainings conducted to equip the teacher for better learning of children. Refresher course conducted by the government to gain the purpose of Ecce.

2. Review of literature

Ecce education is an essential part of education before starting regular class or schooling. It helps to develop the core developmental aspect in child with in this early learning age. Structure of Ecce maintain according to needs of child 3 to 8 year. Different domains are developed by these that help to adjustment of child in next classes. Core development aspect such as, physical development, Social cultural development and learning aspect are developed in children. Physically development, Social development structure include emotion and feeling these helps to adjust in society and control his then emotions. (Erikson, 1950)Nutrients factor also include in the pattern of ecce that help to maintain physically health of child.

Language development initial stage promotes the language skill of child. Children communicate with peers, teachers, and parents that help to improve language skill. It also increases the vocabulary status of child steadily. In Pakistan the Multilanguage used communication. Children enter in school they language such as Urdu, Punjabi, and English so that is a challenge for child for season multi language. Teacher use mixed language to give better understanding

In Pakistan early education need to be develop different initiative taken different institute. Different internal and institute also help to establish a well early education structure like as developed countries Pakistan also tries to improve the early education. NGO's also work for the betterment of the early education. In 2017 Pakistan tries to provide a world class education for early class, so take the steps of ecce.

After passage of from now it make more effect such as ecce classroom establishment. In Pakistan respiratory have mostly research project based on snc and literacy. Limited research is available on ecce initiative. So main focus of research to examine the ecce capability in care development aspect. (Ross, 1976)

2.1. Theoretical framework

Russian psychologists Lev vygostsky said the learning process, and child growth is not possible to ignoring the social and cultural aspects. Children should not learn isolated environment. Teacher and peer interaction help to fast learning and better understanding. According vygostky basic source of learning of child is social relation of children learn from their elder. Children learn from their group peers and friend. (vygostsky, 1978)

Children learn with the help of those who have mastery skills. So the child learns through a proximal development process. In this way a skillful person help the children to solve. Scaffolding also used as technique for children learn. In this way child solve problem in simple to complex pattern. When a child solve easy problem then face some complexity in next stage when child able to solve the problem by him/he self the teacher support removed and student perform individually (Bruner, 1976)

2.2. Physically development aspect early classes

Physically development included gross motor skill, fine motor, skill, hand age condition, sensory development Health nutrients and also body awareness. Children use his/her , arms and legs to play run ,up and down move. Muscles help to coordinate different body parts and provide balance for child. Fine motor skills consist about finger and hands that muscles help to grip the pencil, use scissor for cutting, arranging blocks and colorist things. Hand eye condition helps to utilize the hand and eye at some time for ball grip, catch things and play with toys. Sensory organ used in learning process with help of sense the learn better than a content or lecture with the use of sense cild seen they use and know about texture, smell things and touching the national texture with all these physically skill make strong and help to deny complex task like jumping on stairs and so walk in straight. (Gessell, 1925)

Language development Ecce

Language development is necessary part of education and initial part for adjust in society. Language development in ecce meat able the child to, read, write and speak. According to experts language development occurs in different aspect depend on child age. Babbling stage age 0 - 1 year, when child born that the babbling stage. When child 1- 2 year they used 2 or 3 words. At the age of 2 -3 they speak 2 or 3 words with out resistance. At age of 4-5 the speak a complete sentence. (Charless, 1877). In ecce class teacher used different techniques to develop language. Such as, story telling Rhymes and songs and play based learning.

3. Socio emotional development

Children growth in which children aware about emotion, make relation to others sympathy, behavior control that is socio emotional develop aspect. In socio emotional development child learn about self awareness, self regulate empathy and confidence, relation building. Firstly child learn about him/her self after that control then emotion like as happy, anger and fear. They understand the social interaction with peers and teacher that help to adjust in environment.

Erikson theory of psychosocial help to understand socio cultural adjusts of children in early stage learning. Age of children between 0-1 years is trust vs. mistrust, sometime show trust and some time confused. After these next stage 1 to3 year in which child mood independent they show shame and sometime confident. Children age of 3to6 year try to work himself and take initiative .(Erikson, 1950) In class the social culture activity that make individual more confident is play role, discussion with child, sharing time and teacher guidance support of emotion.

2.4. Global prospective

Early childhood education considers a mile stone for human development because it is not about only future but also hrlp to reduce poverty, illiteracy and promote social equity. 1989 united nation convention focus on the right to childern. In these prospective first right to quality of education. So sustainable development gap help to provide a proper early childhood education structure. The sdgs should be achieved and government of Pakistan works on the goals. Main purpose of the projects to provide universal assess of education, curriculum betterment, teacher training and make learn effect private public partnership. After successful implementation of this benefit the gap to investigate the effectiveness of courses that help to promote development aspect in children in ecce class. This research helps to teacher to promote the aspect of initially development in early childhood education. This study aim to fill the gap by exploring how Examine teacher perceptions regarding capacity building from the prospective of core development aspect in pre Education of children support technique in promptly multiple domain of development in ecce.

2.5. Ecce in Pakistan

In Pakistan ecce class calked katchi class. in these class child age between 3 to 8 admit in ecce class and utilize the source for holistic development of child. Pakistan also follow UNESCO scenario for better early education. for these purpose Pakistan develop the national Education policy framework 2018 that helps to provide single national curriculum 2020. SNC help to provide a equally assessable and quality of education. Implementation of snc all over Pakistan provides a strong nation in future. Ecce project also lunched by the government that provides special decorated room, learning kit, book and learning corner for child. in this way the some restrictions face which some are zero enrollment quality assess, language gaps, infrastructure problem and budget constraint. Government should take step to improve quality of education for increase budget, make Ecce teacher more professionals, parent community awareness compgain and public private partnership. If we improve these so the children adjust in social life and play important role in society Economic

2.6. Research gap

Several studies conducted to examine the professional skills of teacher for early child hood education. Mostly focus this research on pedagogical skills, curriculum suitability and learning experience. However currently available literature limited evidence about the (topic) that helpful for ecce class for different aspect of development. Mostly researches available on childhood education belong to developed countries.

3.1. Statement of problem

Examine the refresher courses for helping ecce teacher to promote the core development aspect in early childhood education students.

3.2. Objectives of study

1. Explore does it help teacher to refresh professional skills for better core development in children?
2. It familiarizes teachers with modern pedagogical utilization in teaching learning.

3.3. Research question

Does the ecce training and refresh courses programme help to enhance capability of teacher in context of development of children according to requirement of bunyad programme?

3.4. Methodology

In this study used Quantative approach because Quantative data will provide a measureable avidance. In this research describe current situation of effectiveness of early childhood care education and examine the current level of ecce for improving purpose.

Population of these studies all ecce teacher whose serving in school and took recently refreshing training in district BWN.

Sample of theses research use cluster sampling in these studies male and female from public institutions.

Survey questionnaire for teacher used for data collection. Questionnaire consist of children are development indicator. Develop a validate research instrument and got permission from the institutions for collecting data.

Analysis using Spss descriptive statics like mean standard deviation frequency AND IN infertial statics use t-test.

4. Data analysis

4.1. Independent T- Test According To Gender

Sr.	Statement	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	P-value
1	The children able to demonstrate coordination of muscles.	Male	75	2.7067	1.38304	2.07	0.040	0.05
		Female	75	2.2667	1.21180			
2	The children use fine motor movement for learning purpose.	Male	75	2.3467	1.10885	1.64	0.103	0.05
		Female	75	2.0667	0.97722			

3	Children use sensorimotor skills when interact in classroom environment.	Male	75	3.0533	1.30377	7.03	0.000	0.05
		Female	75	1.8267	0.76004			
4	Does children conscious about his/her health hygiene	Male	75	2.8133	1.43972	-2.50	0.013	0.05
		Female	75	3.4267	1.56113			
5	Children show feeling and emotion in class.	Male	74	2.8243	1.20908	1.39	0.165	0.05
		Female	75	2.5467	1.22246			
6	Children show affection towards other children by sharing material	Male	75	2.9467	1.36454	-1.49	0.137	0.05
		Female	75	3.2533	1.14010			
7	Does children take care of his/her belonging	Male	75	3.2400	1.45973	7.24	0.000	0.05
		Female	75	1.8533	0.78316			
8	Does children introduce him/her self without hesitation	Male	75	2.9067	1.21002	6.19	0.000	0.05
		Female	75	1.9067	0.70084			
9	Does child participate in group learning	Female	75	3.0267	1.40437	-0.61	0.540	0.05
		Male	75	3.1733	1.51901			
10	Does child notice and watch around in class	Female	75	2.7333	1.31861	1.04	0.298	0.05
		Male	75	2.5200	1.17818			
11	Does children understand the concept of conservation of volume	Female	75	3.4667	1.48263	2.32	0.022	0.05
		Male	75	2.9200	1.40231			
12	Does child have ability to construction of different things in ecce room?	Female	68	3.0294	1.09231	4.76	0.000	0.05
		Male	66	2.1212	1.11652			
13	Does child have equilibrium when walk speedily.	Female	68	2.7794	1.25598	3.06	0.003	0.05
		Male	66	2.1667	1.04636			

1. The mean of sample male (2.70), female (2.36) with standard deviation is (1.48). The result of t- value is (2.07) with significance value (0.04) less than P value 0.05.

2. The mean of sample male (2.34), female (2.06) with standard deviation is (0.97). The result of t- value is (1.64) with significance value (0.10) less than P value 0.05.
3. The mean of sample male (3.05), female (1.30) with standard deviation is (7.03). The result of t- value is (0.01) with significance value (0.00) less than P value 0.05.
4. The mean of sample male (2.81), female (3.42) with standard deviation is (1.43). The result of t- value is (-2.5) with significance value (0.02) less than P value 0.05.
5. The mean of sample male (2.77), female (2.26) with standard deviation is (1.2). The result of t- value is (3.06) with significance value (0.003) less than P value 0.05.
6. The mean of sample male (2.90), female (3.25) with standard deviation is (1.34). The result of t- value is (-1.49) with significance value (0.13) less than P value 0.05.
7. The mean of sample male (3.20), female (1.85) with standard deviation is (1.45). The result of t- value is (7.24) with significance value (0.00) less than P value 0.05.
8. The mean of sample male (2.90), female (1.90) with standard deviation is (1.21). The result of t- value is (6.19) with significance value (0.001) less than P value 0.05.
9. The mean of sample male (3.02), female (3.17) with standard deviation is (1.54). The result of t- value is (-0.61) with significance value (0.54) less than P value 0.05.
10. The mean of sample male (2.73), female (2.52) with standard deviation is (1.31). The result of t- value is (1.04) with significance value (0.29) less than P value 0.05.
11. The mean of sample male (3.46), female (2.92) with standard deviation is (1.50). The result of t- value is (2.32) with significance value (0.02) less than P value 0.05.
12. The mean of sample male (3.02) , female (2.12) with standard deviation is (1.12). The result of t- value is (4.70) with significance value (0.001) less than P value 0.05.
13. The mean of sample male (2.16), female (2.77) with standard deviation is (1.25). The result of t- value is (3.06) with significance value (0.003) less than P value 0.05.

4.2. Independent T- Test According To Geographical Location

Sr.	Statement	Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	P-value
1	The children able to demonstrate coordination of muscles.	Rural	75	2.2667	1.21180	-2.07	0.040	0.05
		Urban	75	2.7067	1.38304			
2	The children use fine motor movement for learning purpose.	Rural	75	2.0667	0.97722	-1.64	0.103	0.05
		Urban	75	2.3467	1.10885			
3	Children use sensorimotor skills when interact in classroom environment.	Rural	75	1.8267	0.76004	-7.03	0.000	0.05
		Urban	75	3.0533	1.30377			

4	Does children conscious about his/her health hygiene	Rural	75	3.4267	1.56113	2.50	0.013	0.05
		Urban	75	2.8133	1.43972			
5	Children show feeling and emotion in class.	Rural	75	2.5467	1.22246	-1.39	0.165	0.05
		Urban	74	2.8243	1.20908			
6	Children show affection towards other children by sharing material	Rural	75	3.2533	1.14010	1.49	0.137	0.05
		Urban	75	2.9467	1.36454			
7	Does children take care of his/her belonging	Rural	75	1.8533	0.78316	-7.24	0.000	0.05
		Urban	75	3.2400	1.45973			
8	Does children introduce him/her self without hesitation	Rural	75	1.9067	0.70084	-6.19	0.000	0.05
		Urban	75	2.9067	1.21002			
9	Does child participate in group learning	Rural	75	3.1733	1.51901	0.61	0.540	0.05
		Urban	75	3.0267	1.40437			
10	Does child notice and watch around in class	Rural	75	2.5200	1.17818	-1.04	0.298	0.05
		Urban	75	2.7333	1.31861			
11	Does children understand the concept of conservation of volume	Rural	75	2.9200	1.40231	-2.32	0.022	0.05
		Urban	75	3.4667	1.48263			
12	Do children have ability to construction of different things in ecce room?	Rural	66	2.1212	1.11652	-4.76	0.000	0.05
		Urban	68	3.0294	1.09231			
13	Does child have equilibrium when walk speedily?	Rural	66	2.1667	1.04636	-3.06	0.003	0.05
		Urban	68	2.7794	1.25598			

Geographical group

1. The mean of sample rural (2.26), urban(2.70) with standard deviation is (1.40). The result of t- value is (-2.07) with significance value (0.04) less than P value 0.05.
2. The mean of sample rural (2.06), urban (2.34) with standard deviation is (1.10). The result of t- value is (-1.64) with significance value (0.10) less than P value 0.05.
3. The mean of sample rural (1.82), urban (3.05) with standard deviation is (1.60). The result of t- value is (-7.03) with significance value (0.00) less than P value 0.05.

4. The mean of sample rural (3.42), urban (2.81) with standard deviation is (1.43). The result of t- value is (2.50) with significance value (0.01) less than P value 0.05.
5. The mean of sample rural (2.16), urban (2.77) with standard deviation is (1.25). The result of t- value is (-3.06) with significance value (0.003) less than P value 0.05.
6. The mean of sample rural (2.54), urban (2.82) with standard deviation is (1.22). The result of t- value is (-1.39) with significance value (0.16) less than P value 0.05.
7. The mean of sample rural (3.25) , urban(2.94) with standard deviation is (1.36). The result of t- value is (1.49) with significance value (0.13) less than P value 0.05.
8. The mean of sample rural (1.85), urban (3.24) with standard deviation is (1.45). The result of t- value is (-7.04) with significance value (0.00) less than P value 0.05.
9. The mean of sample rural (1.90), urban (2.9) with standard deviation is (1.21). The result of t- value is (-6.19) with significance value (0.00) less than P value 0.05.
10. The mean of sample rural (3.17), urban (3.02) with standard deviation is (1.51). The result of t- value is (0.62) with significance value (0.54) less than P value 0.05.
11. The mean of sample rural (2.52), urban (2.73) with standard deviation is (1.41). The result of t- value is (-1.04) with significance value (0.29) less than P value 0.05.
12. The mean of sample rural (2.92), urban (3.42) with standard deviation is (1.50). The result of t- value is (-2.32) with significance value (0.02) less than P value 0.05.
13. The mean of sample rural (2.12) , urban(3.02) with standard deviation is (1.11). The result of t- value is (-4.76) with significance value (0.00) less than P value 0.05

Result

In statically analysis gender wise study, in thirteen only nine statistically significant value differences noted gender wise comparison ($p < 0.05$).In other remain cases, males had higher mean scores than females, while in two cases females scored higher. Overall, males generally demonstrated higher values across most significant measures. In statically analysis geographical wise study, in thirteen only eight statistically significant value differences noted comparison ($p < 0.05$).In other remain cases, urban had higher mean scores than rural. Overall, urban response generally demonstrated higher values across most significant measures.

Discussion

The study show result whose teacher of ecce gain refresher courses, performed better development in children. This finding provides evidence that the training courses help to build the capability of teacher and positive impact on learning and teaching. In some questions surprisingly no significant difference show in gender group and location wise. Some aspect of variable showing significant difference in genfer wise and geographic location. The result show that the focus on teacher refresher course for capacity building paly intial role for improvement core development aspect. The stdy limited to a district Bahawalnagar and respective tehsil.which generalized ability of result. In future ths studies help to explore more aspect of development that helps to maintain the effectiveness learning gor children.

Summary

The study related to teacher perception regarding capacity building. Main purpose of these study about perception of teacher for core development aspect of children education. Research studies find out the effectiveness of refresher courses for teacher early education. Descriptive studies include quantitative analysis. A questionnaire tool use for collect data for sample and cluster sampling technique use for these studies. Population of this study school teacher male and female whose teaching in ecce. Spss 27 use for data analysis in descriptive statistics use mean and standard deviation, inferential statistics use compare to means group by independent t test. Findings of this research according to three core aspects have significant difference but some aspect have no significant affects in both gender and geographic location. Conclusion from this study refresher courses are essential factor for improving capacity building of teacher for betterment of ecce. In future different aspect of development in child and capacity build perception need to be search that make learning more effective for society.

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